

Towards a Bioinspired Soft Robotic Gripper for Gentle Manipulation of Mushrooms

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Abstract—Soft Robotics showed great potential in applications where safety and compliance are key factors for the interaction of the robot with delicate objects and the environment. Mushroom harvesting nowadays is mainly performed by human harvesters and requires both dexterity and a gentle touch to preserve the quality of fresh products. Indeed, improper contact may lead to blemishes on the mushroom surface representing a loss for the market. The inherent mechanical compliance of soft grippers is a major advantage for gripping delicate produce, as the soft robotic structure can passively conform around the object to distribute its contact load, however clear specifications on the maximum forces that can be exerted are crucial for the design. This work presents a soft finger-based pneumatic gripper inspired by human hand capabilities in the manipulation of white button mushrooms, with the final aim of integrating into a robotic platform to automate the mushroom picking process. Bruising analysis on fresh mushrooms has been performed to evaluate the range of normal force that can be exerted without causing damage to the fresh products. The results show that mushroom cell walls can tolerate normal forces up to 7 N without breaking and exhibiting bruises. This value is significantly higher than the average normal force exerted by the expert harvester (2-3 N) and it should be considered as the upper limit of the normal force which can be exerted by the gripper. These preliminary results pave the way to integrate the proposed soft gripper into mushroom shelves as the first step towards the automatizing of the harvesting process.

Index Terms—Soft Robotics, Soft Gripper, Bruising analysis, *Agaricus bisporus*

I. INTRODUCTION

Robotic systems that efficiently handle delicate objects can be used in a broad and diverse range of production applications, with tremendous economic benefits [1] [2]. For instance, using robots to manipulate fragile products in the horticulture sector could reduce labor costs, boost productivity, and improve working conditions [3]. In particular, the mushroom industry is under growing pressure due to high labor

costs which can account for 40% of production costs [4]. The white button mushroom *Agaricus bisporus* is the fifth most widely cultivated mushroom in the world accounting for 11-15% of global production (4.4 - 4.7 million tonnes) between 2013 and 2018-19 [5]. In Europe, *A. bisporus* production in 2020 was 1.24 million tonnes of which approx 65% was harvested by hand for the fresh market and 35% for the processed market [6]. Mushrooms for canning and freezing can be harvested mechanically and handled by an automated system, but such automation does not yet exist for picking and handling mushrooms for the fresh market, due to the high-quality standards required for this product. Harvesting fresh food products such as mushrooms is a routine, repetitive task requiring skill and speed. Harvesting conditions can be challenging – working in narrow spaces at high humidity (Fig.1) - and can vary from country to country but in recent years there have been several innovations, such as the ‘single layer’ system, ‘tilted shelves’ and ‘two-handed picking onto conveyors’, that have made the harvesting job easier. Nonetheless, sourcing and retaining labor for this demanding work across Europe and globally in recent years has been challenging [7] [8]. Starting salaries are generally at the minimum wage although working conditions can vary from country to country. While downstream elements of the process can be automated, the actual picking of fresh mushrooms is still done manually, due to the dexterity, precision, and sensitivity of the human hand that can pick the mushroom and not damage it [9]. The horticulture sector, in general, is looking increasingly towards automation and robotics to help manage labor shortages [10]. Robotic harvesting systems for fresh mushrooms have been developed in the past but to date, none meet the exacting quality demands of the marketplace [11] [12]. Mushrooms have a soft body and can be easily damaged and bruised by external forces. Indeed, mushrooms can be easily damaged by conventional gripper designs and present high variability across multiple factors such as orientation

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Fig. 1: Working conditions of a harvester in the process of picking mushrooms in cultivation shelves.

and root strength. Browning and discoloration of mushrooms can occur at various times during the crop and supply chain. Bruising development is due to mushroom cell wall breakdown and the consequent exposure of polyphenols to oxygen. The presence of polyphenol oxidases allows the oxygen to oxidize the phenolic substrates into quinones, followed by the formation of the pigment melanin [13]. Conventional rigid end-effectors are ill-suited for the manipulation of delicate organic objects in such a dense environment, as they are likely to damage both the collected target and mushrooms growing adjacent to it. In addition, a conventional rigid end-effector requires high-resolution position and force sensors and precise transmission systems to avoid damaging the delicate object [14]. Prior attempts have been made to eliminate the rigid end-effector by employing robotic vacuum end-effectors [15]. This solution has proven only partially successful, as gripping forces applied to the cap surface can still be excessive due to the limited contact area of the suction cup. It is known that a source of discoloration due to contact is the “slip-shear” force at picking [16], but little is known about the potential damage due to pure normal force. Optimizing the conventional suction cup designs is not likely to fully eliminate damage inflicted on mushrooms due to the high variability in mushroom size, orientation, and cluster density. To overcome the challenges of delicate grasp actuation and high-resolution sensing, the EU-funded SoftGrip project proposes a solution based on soft robotic structures comprised of elastomeric materials that deform in a distributed and continuous manner [17]. This inherent mechanical compliance is a major advantage for gripping delicate produce, as the soft robotic structure can passively morph and conform around the object to distribute its contact load [14]. In particular, finger-based soft grippers offer large joint deformations extending the range of motion and ultimately seek to replicate the high dexterity of manipulation which is seen in the human hand and have been successfully applied to harvesting vegetables and fruit [14] [18]. In this work, bruising analysis is carried out on fresh mushrooms to assess the safe range of normal force that they can sustain with minimal bruising, and a soft robotic gripper made of elastomeric materials is proposed for gentle manipulation of mushrooms. The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. In section II, we introduce the bruising analysis for

normal forces as well as the design of the gripper and the FEM model of the finger to derive the bending angle and tip force. We also introduce the experimental setup used for the characterization of the performance of the finger. In section III, we present and discuss the experimental results of the discoloration test on mushrooms as well as the tip force of the finger. Finally, in section IV, we draw our conclusions on the work.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Design of the soft gripper

The design of the soft gripper is based on the study of the hand-picking motion during mushroom harvesting. According to expert harvesters, the hand-picking procedure is commonly based on three fingers (the thumb, the index, and the middle). This leads to the design shown in Fig.2 featuring a 3D-printed palm (ProJet MJP 3600, 3D systems, USA) Fig.2A that connects three equal soft-bending actuators Fig.2B. The configuration of a human hand regarding size has been adopted for targeting mushrooms in the 40-60 mm cap diameter. In particular, the soft finger hereby presented is a Pneumatic Network (Pneu-net) bending actuator [19]. Pneu-net bending actuators comprise two main components, namely the upper and bottom layers. The upper layer consists of a series of hollow chambers connected via a longitudinal channel, whereas the bottom layer consists of a thicker sheet of material that seals the chambers. Upon the application of positive pressure, the chambers - fabricated from elastomeric material - inflate, causing the thinner longitudinal walls to expand and push onto each other. The thicker bottom layer integrating a strain-limiting layer sheet (Polyethylene terephthalate PET-FO-A4, Felga Etichette, Italy) provides a mechanical constraint that promotes the planar bending of the structure and forces the bending direction inward. The mechanical design is completed by a solid structure in the proximal part of the actuator with a groove to allow simple interlocking with a rigid attachment structure and by a short flap in the distal part to allow for future integration of contact sensors. The tapering morphology (variable height of the finger) has been chosen to address the shape adaptability ability for mushroom harvesting of the soft finger as well as to reduce the dimension of the finger, especially at the fingertip. Indeed, for the intended application, compactness of the gripper is required due to the stringent size constraints for mounting the gripper at the level of the cultivation shelves. Moreover, rounding the edges of the internal chambers may allow for a reduction in the concentration of stress once positive pressure is applied to the internal walls for inflation of the finger. The design of the finger, as well as the relevant dimensions, is shown in Fig.2B. The design resulted from a heuristic strategy aiming at maximizing the bending angle, favoring the compactness of the finger while considering the physical limitations of the manufacturing process.

Fig. 2: Design of the soft gripper (A) 3D printed palm (B) soft finger and relevant dimensions

B. FEM model

To support the design of the gripper we have implemented a FEM model of the soft finger. The model has been developed with the Static Structural Analysis tool of ANSYS Workbench using the real dimensions of the finger reported in Fig.2B. The material used for the manufacturing of the finger is Dragon Skin 30-A silicone rubber. In the simulation, it has been virtualized using a 3rd order Yeoh model for hyperelastic, incompressible materials with the following strain energy function:

$$U = \sum_{i=1}^3 C_i (I_1 - 3)^i$$

where C_i are the material coefficients and I_1 is the first strain invariant. The coefficients were identified by fitting the model to the experimental data obtained through standard uniaxial tensile tests (ASTM D142) at a rate of 200 mm/min and resulted to be $C_1 = 0.01039$, $C_2 = -0.00037$ and $C_3 = 0.00011$ MPa. The PET layer is modeled as a linear elastic material with Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio of $E_s = 350$ MPa and 0.4, respectively. As boundary conditions, the finger is fixed at one end, pressure is applied on the inner walls to simulate the air input, and the effect of the standard earth gravity is considered. FEM simulations are conducted to estimate the bending behavior of the actuator as well as the tip force that the finger may exert in contact with a rigid object.

C. Fabrication

The fabrication of the finger consists of a multi-step open molding procedure. The molds have been designed using SolidWorks and 3D-printed using a ProJet MJP 3600 from 3D Systems. The two reagents of the Dragon Skin 30A silicone rubber have been mixed in equal parts, degassed in a vacuum oven, and poured into the molds for the upper and bottom layers, this latter integrates also the PET sheet. The parts are cured at room temperature and demoulded. Finally, the upper and bottom parts are joined using a small quantity of uncured silicone and inserting the pipe for the air.

D. Force test and color response on mushrooms

To estimate the range of normal force that the gripper can exert on mushrooms without causing any damage or quality

loss, the resistance of mushroom caps to normal force was assessed. 100 mushrooms (*A. bisporus*) were picked daily for 5 days and then immediately brought to the laboratory for the force tests. The size of the mushroom caps was 55 ± 5 mm. The stalks were removed completely and the mushroom caps were placed in a TA.TXplus texture analyzer (Stable Micro Systems, Godalming, Surrey, United Kingdom,) shown in Fig.3 mount with a 6 mm diameter cylindrical effector. The treatments applied to the mushrooms daily are given in Tab.1. The tests were repeated on a new set of mushrooms over five days. The range of forces selected for testing was chosen based on real data from mushroom hand-picking. The amount of force needed for successful harvesting depends on several factors (e.g. crop stage, the rooting depth, the presence of mushroom clusters, and mushroom size). A preliminary evaluation before this work showed that the minimum normal force required for successful picking by expert harvesters is in the range of 2-3 N. A mushroom with strong roots may require a brief peak of 5N to be outrooted, while 7N represents an unnecessary amount of force to achieve the mushroom outrooting. We decided to assess the force rather than the pressure to evaluate the bruising since the soft gripper will be equipped with force sensors at the level of each fingertip. This makes the results easily comparable to those recorded during the human picking sessions. Furthermore, while the pressure can be easily calculated for a rigid body like the effector we installed in the texture analyzer, it would be complicated to accurately calculate the contact surface between the human finger and/or the soft gripper's finger and the mushroom, as many factors would influence the deformation of those surfaces. The application time of the normal force is overestimated intentionally concerning the one of a soft gripper, to understand the possible negative effects of handling the mushrooms for too long. The normal force was applied at the center of the cap and the area was marked to allow the identification of the tested area in case of no visible change in color at the end of the incubation time. The mushrooms were placed in 250g commercial plastic punnets (JFMcKenna, Armagh, United Kindom), sealed with perforated film (JFMcKenna, Armagh, United Kindom), and incubated at room temperature for 48 hours, avoiding any shaking that could cause unwanted damages to the mushrooms. These storage conditions are designed to enhance the development of discoloration following mechanical damage and bruising. Furthermore, Weijin et al. [13] demonstrated that mushrooms subjected to controlled mechanical damage develop visible bruising after 60 minutes. At the end of the incubation, the color response of the tested area was assessed using a Konica-Minolta CR-400 Chromameter (Konica Minolta Business Solutions Europe GmbH) in the CIELab color space (ISO 11664-4:2008(en) Colorimetry — Part 4: CIE 1976 Lab Colour space). The color data were computed according to the methodology used in [20]. A ΔE 'color distance' value was calculated for each mushroom to assess the difference between the sample and an ideal value that represents a mushroom of excellent quality. Data were analyzed by two-way ANOVA. ΔE values for each treatment group were then compared to

Fig. 3: Experimental setup for the application of normal forces to mushroom caps color assessment using a TA.TXplus texture analyzer.

the control untreated mushrooms. The closer the ΔE value is to 0 the whiter the mushroom being measured.

TABLE I: Daily treatment pattern applied to freshly picked mushrooms with a commercial size of 55 ± 5 mm diameter. This treatment pattern was repeated for 5 pick days.

Samples	Nominal pressure (g)	Normal Force (N)	Application Time (s)
10	Control (0)	Control (0)	Control (0)
10	100	3	5
10	100	3	10
10	100	3	15
10	150	5	5
10	150	5	10
10	150	5	15
10	200	7	5
10	200	7	10
10	200	7	15

E. Bending test

To validate our design, we have developed an experimental setup to measure the bending behavior of the finger for different actuation pressures. The finger has been mounted on a platform with a 3D-printed fixture and an HD camera has been used to capture the finger's planar bending motion. For the fluidic actuation of the air input, the pressure has been controlled by a proportional pressure regulator (K8P-0-D522-0, Camozzi Group) directly connected to an air compressor (Leonardo 101, FIAC S.p.A.).

F. Tip force test

Another important performance factor to assess for soft bending actuators is the tip force in the normal direction to the finger to evaluate the grasping capability of the soft gripper. To measure the tip force, we have developed the experimental setup shown in Fig.4 Regarding the actuation for

Fig. 4: Experimental setup for tip force test with the soft finger in rest condition

the air the equipment described in the previous paragraph has been used. The experimental setup for the tip force test consists of attaching the proximal end of the actuator vertically with the fingertip attached to a 3D printed support mounted on a 6-axis load cell (ATI Industrial Automation, USA) as depicted in Fig.4. The experimental protocol consists of pressurizing the finger up to 1 bar with steps of 0.2 bar and recording the force measurements from the load cell. The tests were repeated three times for each pressure value and the value of the tip force (in direction x in Fig.4) is compared with the results obtained with the FEM model under the same conditions.

III. RESULTS

A. Force and color response on mushrooms

The two-way ANOVA of the total dataset indicated that there was no statistical difference between the force treatments tested and the control subset for all the tested conditions in terms of ΔE value ($p > 0.05$, Fig.5). This means that the range of normal forces applied for the time intervals tested was not able to cause any discoloration. Therefore, the results show that the tested range of normal force up to 7 N is not a limiting factor in the design of a soft robotic gripper for mushroom harvesting.

Fig. 5: Results of color assessment in terms of ΔE for all the tested conditions

B. Bending test

Fig.6 reports the relationship between the air pressure and the bending angle θ of the soft actuator. The experimental

results of the actual actuator are close to the FEM simulation results. The bending angle increases with the pressure reaching at $p = 0.7$ bar about 120° . When it increases to a certain extent, the sensitivity of the bending angle to pressure, changes become weaker and the bending angle changes slowly and very closely to the simulation results.

Fig. 6: Relationship between the bending angle θ and the input pressure p . Experimental and FEM results are reported respectively in red and blue.

C. Tip force test

The results in terms of tip force F_{tip} are reported in Fig.7 together with the ones obtained in the simulation. As expected, the tip measured by the load cell increases with increasing values of air input pressure. A good correspondence is observed between simulations and experimental data, with the former slightly overestimating the latter. The maximum value reached by the finger is about 3 N at 1 bar.

IV. CONCLUSION

The fresh mushroom industry is highly labor-intensive and the labor costs have a huge impact on the production cost. So far robotic automation for picking delicate fresh produce has been quite difficult mainly due to the complex, contact-rich interactions involved in such a task. Indeed, nowadays mushroom picking is mostly performed by human harvesters.

Fig. 7: Relationship between the tip force F_{tip} and the input pressure p . Experimental and FEM results are reported respectively in red and blue.

The first step toward automatizing the harvesting procedure is developing suitable end-effectors that may replicate the compliance and dexterity of human hands. Indeed, mushrooms might be easily damaged by conventional gripper design that with improper contact may determine blemishes and bruising on the mushroom surface. Soft grippers can provide the gentle touch required for mushroom harvesting replacing also the need for precise sensor-based control of rigid grippers. Moreover, the inherent adaptability and simple control make soft grippers a good candidate for cluttered and unstructured environments such as the occluded canopy of most mushroom crops. This work introduces a pneumatically actuated soft robotic gripper for the gentle manipulation of delicate white button mushrooms. To properly dimension the fingers of the gripper, a bruising analysis on white button mushrooms due to the application of normal forces has been carried out. Results showed that fresh mushrooms can sustain a normal force of up to 7 N without showing any significant color change. Later, the soft finger has been characterized in terms of bending angle and tip force. Further investigation is required to understand the role of tangential forces and handling time in the generation of discoloration. Moreover, the future integration of soft bending sensors and force sensors into the soft gripper may allow the implementation of a closed-loop control strategy for mushroom harvesting. These preliminary results pave the way for mounting the soft gripper as an end effector of a cartesian robot positioned on the cultivation shelf of mushroom crops.

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